

CAT-UI E2E Test cases

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UI Testing Frameworks

Frameworks options for functional testing:

- Cypress - [React docs](#)
- Selenium - [docs](#)
- Cucumber - [docs](#)
- Puppeteer - [docs](#)

Framework options for visual testing:

- <https://applitools.com>
- <https://percy.io/>
- <https://github.com/garris/BackstopJS>

CAT-UI Test cases table

Test file/page	PR number	PR status	Test cases
Admin	148	Merged	- Accept a validation request - Declines a validation request

Assessment	135 & 152	Merged	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greets with create assessment - Brings me back to assessments - Has the correct actor option - Can go to step 2 and go back - Makes the submitter fields readonly - Create an assessment
Sign in	145	Merged	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greets with sign in - Requires username - Requires password - Logs in
Profile	146	Merged	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Checks an identified user profile information - Does not allow validations without updating details - Does not show assessments/subjects without validation - Links to validations - Links to assessments - Links to subjects - Requires the required fields to be filled out - Requires the name to be longer than 3 characters - Does not require an ORCID id - Updates the personal details
Subject	147	Merged	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deletes a subject - Edits a subject - Greets with create new subject - Closes the modal - Creates a subject
Validation	148	Merged	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creates a validation - Creates a validation with a custom organization

Admin

The following test cases are found in the [admin.cy.ts](#) file.

Accept a validation request

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User logs in as admin and navigates to profile page	Valid admin credentials	User arrives on profile page
2	User navigates to validations page		User arrives on validations page
3	User clicks approve icon for a validation request	Validation request that is ready for approval	User is asked to confirm validation
4	User confirms validation		System notifies the user that the validation has been approved successfully.

Declines a validation request

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User logs in as admin and navigates to profile page	Valid admin credentials	User arrives on profile page
2	User navigates to validations page		User arrives on validations page
3	User clicks reject icon for a validation request	Invalid validation request	User is asked to confirm rejection
4	User confirms rejection		System notifies the user that the validation has been rejected successfully.

Assessment

The following test cases are found in the [assessment.cy.ts](#) file.

Greets with create assessment

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User logs in	Valid credentials	User arrives on profile page
2	User navigates to assessments creation page		User arrives on assessments creation page

Brings me back to assess

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User clicks on back button	User has successfully navigated to assessment creation page	User arrives on assessment overview page

Has the correct actor option

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User is able to select an organization on the create assessment page.	User has successfully navigated to the assessment creation page. And there is an organization available for assessment.	

Can go to step 2 and go back

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User navigates to assessments creation page	Valid credentials	User arrives on assessments creation page
2	User selects the organization they want to create an assessment for	There is an organization available for assessment.	
3	User selects organization		Bullet at selected organization becomes highlighted
4	User clicks create button		User arrives at step 2
5	User clicks on back button		User arrives at step 1

Makes the submitter fields readonly

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User navigates to assessments creation page	Valid credentials	User arrives on assessments creation page
2	User selects the organization they want to create an assessment for	There is an organization available for assessment.	
3	User selects organization		Bullet at selected organization becomes highlighted

4	User clicks create button		User arrives at step 2
5	Submitter accordion shows read only text		User is unable to change read only text

Create an assessment

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User navigates to assessments creation page	Valid credentials	User arrives on assessments creation page
2	User selects the organization they want to create an assessment for	There is an organization available for assessment.	
3	User selects organization		Bullet at selected organization becomes highlighted
4	User clicks create button		User arrives at step 2
5	User fills in all required fields in each step		User is shown submit button
6	User creates new assessment by clicking the submit button	Valid assessment creation form	System confirms that a new assessment has been created. User is routed back to the assessments page.

Sign In

The following test cases are found in the [login.cy.ts](#) file.

The terms "sign in" and "login" are interchangeable.

Greets with sign in

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to login page	User is currently signed out.	User is is shown sign in form

Requires username

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to login page	User is currently signed out.	User is is shown login form
2	User clicks login button		User is shown an error: "Invalid username or password."

Requires password

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to login page	User is currently signed out.	User is is shown login form
2	User clicks login button		User is shown an error: "Invalid username or password."

Logs in

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the login page	User is currently signed out.	User is shown login form
2	User fills in username and password	Valid account credentials	
3	User clicks login button		User is shown profile instead of login form on the /login page

Profile

The following test cases are found in the [profile.cy.ts](#) file.

Checks an identified user profile information

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the profile page	Valid account credentials	User lands on profile page. User can inspect their profile details

Does not allow validations without updating details

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the profile page	Valid account credentials	User lands on profile page. User can inspect their profile details
2	User checks if they are allowed to create validation requests	User's account is unable to create validation request	System shows warning that user is unable to create validation request

Does not show assessments/subjects without validation

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the profile page	Valid account credentials	User lands on profile page. User can inspect their profile details
2	User checks if they are allowed to create validation requests	User's account is able to create validation request	User is shown the options to see their validation requests or start a new one

Links to validations

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the profile page	Valid account credentials	User lands on profile page. User can inspect their profile details
2	User checks if they are allowed to create validation requests	User's account is able to create validation request	User is shown the options to see their validation requests or start a new one
3	User clicks "list" button in the Validation Requests block		User is routed to the assessment overview page

Links to assessments

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the profile page	Valid account credentials	User lands on profile page. User can inspect their profile details
2	User checks if they are allowed to create validation requests	User's account is able to create validation request	User is shown the options to see their validation requests or start a new one

3	User clicks "create new" button in the Assessments block		User is routed to the assessment creation page.
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Links to subjects

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the profile page	Valid account credentials	User lands on profile page. User can inspect their profile details
2	User checks if they are allowed to create validation requests	User's account is able to create validation request	User is shown the options to see their validation requests or start a new one
3	User clicks "create new" button in the Subjects block		User is routed to the subjects creation page.

Requires the required fields to be filled out

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the profile update page	Valid account credentials	User lands on profile update page
2	User clicks submit button	None of the fields have been filled in	System highlights required fields

Requires the name to be longer than 3 characters

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the profile update page	Valid account credentials	User lands on profile update page
2	User fills in all required fields correctly except for the name field	Name field contains less than 3 characters.	
3	User clicks submit button		System notifies that name must be at least three characters

Does not require an ORCID id

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the profile update page	Valid account credentials	User lands on profile update page
2	User fills in all required fields correctly except for the name field	ORCID field is left empty	
3	User clicks submit button		System notifies user that their profile has been updated

Updates the personal details

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the profile update page	Valid account credentials	User lands on profile update page
2	User fills in all required fields correctly		
3	User clicks submit button		System notifies user that their profile has been updated

Subject

The following test cases are found in the [subject.cy.ts](#) file.

Deletes a subject

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the objects page	Valid account credentials and objects	User lands on object management page
2	User clicks delete button for a subject		System ask for confirmation
3	User confirms		System notifies user that the subject has been deleted

Edits a subject

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the objects page	Valid account credentials and an object	User lands on object's management page
2	User clicks edit button		System show edit subject modal
3	User updates subject		
4	User clicks update button		System notifies user that the subject has been updated

Greet with create new subject

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the objects page	Valid account credentials	User lands on objects page
2	User clicks create new button		System show create new subject modal

Closes the modal

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the objects page	Valid account credentials	User lands on objects page
2	User clicks create new button		System show create new subject modal
3	User closes the modal		No new subject has been created

Creates a subject

All three fields of the subject are required. There are test in place that check if a subject can be created without filling in one of the fields.

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the objects page	Valid account credentials	User lands on objects page
2	User clicks create new button		System show create new subject modal
3	User fills in the form	All fields are filled in correctly	
4	User clicks create button		System notifies user that new subject has been created

Validation

The following test cases are found in the [validation.cy.ts](#) file.

Creates a validation

In this test case the user selects a pre-existing organization from a dropdown list.

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the validation creation page	Valid account credentials	User lands on validation creation page
2	User fills in form	All fields are filled in correctly	
3	User clicks submit button		System notifies user that new validation request has been created

Creates a validation with a custom organization

In this test case the user fills in a new organization instead of choosing from a dropdown list.

Step	Description	Requirements	Expected outcomes
1	User browses to the validation creation page	Valid account credentials	User lands on validation creation page
2	User fills in form	All fields are filled in correctly	
3	User clicks submit button		System notifies user that new validation request has been created

Old Use Cases

Left out of this document. You may find them [here](#)